

THE ROLE OF THE LATEST APPROACHES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR APPLICATION WORLDWIDE

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Annotatsiya: The issue of applying an open way to deal with foreign language instructing of understudies in non-language branches of advanced education foundations in various nations has been examined in the paper. It has been noticed that the communicative approach, in light of intuitive techniques for educating and establishing the climate of normal language climate at class, shapes the teaching of language preparation in the USA, Malaysia, Serbia, Croatia, and in the greater part of West European nations. In China and Saudi Arabia, open way to deal with foreign language education is joined with a conventional strategy to foster a wide range of discourse movements. It has been validated that limiting the syntax part of understudies' foreign language preparation for framing just open abilities has brought to familiar yet linguistically wrong discourse. It has been demonstrated that the viability of foreign language instructing to an extensive degree relies upon applying the coordinated preparation framework because of customary didactics and communicative approaches.

Kalit so'zlar: foreign language teaching, communicative approach, traditional method, grammar structure, communicative competence, interactive training, natural language environment, foreign language proficiency.

The strengthening of worldwide mix processes, remembering the extension of global participation for different circles of expert exercises, is one of the main components of the current perspective. Because of these cycles, it ought to be noticed that the public interest in experts with an adequate degree of foreign language capability is continually expanding. Applying an open way to deal with foreign language education of understudies in non-language branches of advanced education foundations, which is generally acknowledged in numerous nations, is the best approach to framing proficient foreign language open capability of future experts in a specific field. In any case, one shouldn't disregard the way that the previously mentioned approach enjoys clear benefits as well as various questionable focuses which will be viewed in this paper. The point of the paper is to break down the historical backdrop of open methodology as well as to sum up the aftereffects of hypothetical examination and world experience of applying informative ways to deal with foreign language

education. The idiosyncrasies of applying an open way to deal with preparing are viewed as underway by P. Bekh, I. Bim, H. Hez, H. Kytaihorodska, O. Leontyev, H. Rohova, I. Zymnia. [1]

The issue of shaping the foreign language open capability of understudies is introduced in the investigations of T. Astafurova, T. MacArthur, and Ye. Passov. The expert constituent of foreign language preparation is highlighted by A. Andriienko, E. Bibikova, K. Klimenko, and S. Kozak. The issues of characterizing the quintessence and explaining the design of expert foreign language skills are taken up in the progress of H. Arkhipova, Yu. Fedorenko, O. Pavlenko, N. Prudnikova and others. Such strategies as examination, amalgamation, correlation, systematization, and speculation of hypothetical and useful experiences of foreign language showing in different nations structure the premise of this exploration. Open way to deal with foreign language preparation specifies demonstrating average informative circumstances. As indicated by the translation of R. Milrud and me. Maksymova this approach is instructing, and coordinated based on finishing informative responsibilities.

It is important to express that the vast majority of specialists (L. Bachman, C. Candlin, J. Richards, T. Rodgers, and others) concur that informative methodology ought to be designated “approach”, not “technique” because, as indicated by J. Richards, the approach is a lot more extensive than technique. The approach is an intricate classification, which characterizes the methodology as well as the decision of preparing techniques, which understand this procedure and give the fluctuation of its translations. Regardless of the laid out assessment that D. Hymes is the pioneer behind open hypothesis, J. Richards and T. Rodgers have demonstrated that the starting points of open methodology can be tracked down in the American convention of the 1930s, as for which preparing was coordinated with a look to the necessities of future expert correspondence.

The information of the examination of academic writing, committed to the issues of shaping and improvement of an open way to deal with schooling, let us declare that inside the period from the 1930s till 1960s the need for foreign language educating was continuously moving to the informative methodology, which depended on audiolingual and situational preparing techniques, that included applying informative errands, associated with a specific setting. Inside

¹ Acar, A., Memedova, B., Rzayev, H. & Sekerci, O. (2005). A Critical Review of Hymes' on Communicative Competence. In: Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Modern Approaches Methods and ELT problems (5.–7.09.2005). Isparta : SDU Printing Centre, pp. 57–68.

the accompanying stage, the hypothetical issues of foreign language education were explained and on second thought of dominating just punctuation rules and learning lexical units, the open ability of understudies was shaped and created. That period was portrayed by uncovering the job and primary highlights of informative methodology as well as the mental and academic states of its application were characterized. A. Howatt referred to that period as “open unrest”. By the by, this perspective is disputable. In this setting, the expression “unrest” (from the Latin revolution - “upset”) should be determined. The expression “insurgency” signifies the complete liquidation of something old and the presentation of a genuinely new thing, which is further developed.

In this manner, considering the way that the starting points of open methodology can be followed back inside the period from the 1930s to 1960s, as for K. Johnson the phase of the supposed “open transformation” is the continuation of the resulting formative phase of existing language instructing customs. There is no question that the purported “open time” brought about the strength of an open way to deal with the foreign language preparation of understudies in numerous nations. By and by, the period since the year 2000 can be portrayed as “post-communicative time” (A. Acar) which is the phase of changing the primary thoughts of informative methodology. In the most recent examinations, the researchers have made endeavors to rethink the by and large acknowledged confidence in verifiable adequacy of an open way to deal with foreign language education. In this way, such analysts as S. Bax, A. Occasion, D. Tracker, J. Richards, and C. Samimy have raised an issue, which is vital for every one of the nations, where foreign languages are shown based on open methodology. [2]

The issue is as for the following: whether it is sensible to apply the before referenced approach similarly in all nations, regardless of the quirks of attitude, culture, and language capability of understudies that to send out this way to deal with all nations and copy it with practically no changes. C. Samimy stresses that the model of open skill that exists in the advanced world has been worked out for the most part by American researchers that is by local speakers to foster the informative abilities of local speakers. This model depends on the language standards and on the particular sociocultural highlights and instructive norms which are common in the US. This multitude of viewpoints at times make

² Basta, J. (2011). The Role of the Communicative Approach and Cooperative Learning in Higher Education. *Facta Universitatis. Ser. Linguistics and Literature*, Volume 9, No 2, pp. 125–143.

challenges educators in different nations while acquainting this methodology by showing English as a foreign language. At present on the planet, in the scholastic local areas, one can frequently hear basic remarks on the way that successfully framing the foreign language open capability of understudies relies upon applying just informative way to deal with preparing. Researchers from numerous nations concur that at first D. Hymes' hypothesis of framing open capability was something like an analysis of N. Chomsky's semantic hypothesis and not the endeavor of making a new tenet in language education.

Specifically, A. Acar disagrees with D. Hymes' analysis that there is a compelling reason need to realize the punctuation rules of a language, on the off chance that they are not utilized in viable discourse movement. Analysts stress that the capability approach ought to be founded on N. Chomsky's semantic skill which is essential to the informative capability because the "open way to deal with a language begins with the language hypothesis as the language of correspondence". For this situation dominating the hypothetical essentials of a foreign language surmises that understudies comprehend its syntax structure, which is the premise of fostering the abilities of syntactically right discourse. Solely after this, it is applicable to talk about carrying out key standards of informative methodology in class, which are the following: problematic, situational, and proficient orientability. ^[3]

What's more, with that, Chinese educators additionally consider the propensities to modifying the uniqueness and all-inclusiveness of the previously mentioned approach. They note that alongside zeroing in on the open part that is framing tuning in and talking abilities, focusing closer on punctuation and writing is fundamental. A ton of researchers from Japan and Saudi Arabia likewise hold a comparable assessment. At Japanese colleges along with the open way to deal with showing foreign languages, educators apply conventional strategies to foster the abilities in perusing and composing. English researchers, like C. Henner-Stanchina, H. Holec, and P. Riley, are of the interval sees on this issue. They consider that language instructive climate is the best essential for effective foreign language education, in which joining both conventional strategy and open approach is conceivable.

In this way, notwithstanding the way that because of commonsense requests of development the principal objective of present-day language preparation is as yet shaping open abilities, learning a foreign language just at

³ Chen, G., Starosta, W. (2008). Intercultural Communication Competence: A synthesis. The Global Intercultural Communication Reader, pp. 215–237.

the degree of useful proficiency brings to dominating a crude “endurance language”. It is applicable to stress that applying the open methodology in class doesn't mean reformatting the substance of foreign language instruction. For this situation we ought to talk just about utilizing new, more compelling techniques pointed toward creating foreign language open abilities of understudies. Thusly, regardless of the way that up to now the delegates of world educational local area have not completely concurred at this point, possibly it is sensible to apply or to disregard conventional strategies for foreign language showing for the main open methodology, we accept that the best consequences of preparing can be achieved given applying a mind boggling framework which ought to incorporate both the components of customary techniques and of imaginative methodologies in educating. In further examination, we are intending to concentrate on the points of view of showing a foreign language with the assistance of data innovations.

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